

Effective of Health Education Program in Knowledge, Attitudes and Practice of Diabetic Septic Foot Patients to Prevent Foot Ulcers at King Fahd General Hospital Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (2018 to 2021)

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Abstract

Diabetes is the most common chronic disease worldwide. Although many serious complications can affect the individual with diabetes, foot problems take the greatest. This is an interventional quasi-experimental hospital-based study was conduct in King Fahd General Hospital in Jeddah, king of Saudi Arabia aimed at assessing the effective of health education program in knowledge, attitudes and practice of diabetic septic foot patient to prevent foot ulcer. Sixty diabetic ulcers patients were participating in this study during the period of the study from July 2018 to July 2021. The data was collected by using a questionnaire. The data was analyzed by using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). The study results evident that the percentage of knowledge regarding diabetic septic foot patient to prevent foot ulcer for all items of diabetic septic foot care, were improved after the training program. The results of study regarding knowledge of patients to cause of diabetic foot ulcers were highly increased in percentages in post-intervention compared to pre-intervention. The results regarding education of risk factors of diabetic patients were increased in percentage in post-intervention compared to pre-intervention in education program for correct questions, but for incorrect it decreased also same results were presented in surgical management. The study concluded that there was significant improvement in patients' knowledge attitude and practice regarding diabetic septic foot care after the education program. So the study recommended that continuing education program for diabetic septic foot patients is very important, learning facilities (books, Journals) about diabetic septic foot care should be available at hospitals

Introduction

Diabetic foot ulcers are a devastating component of diabetes progression affecting about 15% of patients with diabetes. The underlying pathophysiology of diabetic foot ulcers is a complex interplay between the body's persistent hyperglycemic state and that of neuropathic, vascular and immune system components [1]. Preventative strategies in the form of patient education and regular foot assessments for diabetic patients along with risk stratification form the basis of

the management of diabetic foot disease [2]. However, a combination of a number of treatment modalities can also be facilitated by the multidisciplinary team for those with more complex diabetic foot complications. Therefore, preventative strategies including annual diabetic foot screening and diabetic foot care interventions facilitated through a multidisciplinary team have been implemented to enable early identification of diabetic patients at high risk of diabetic foot complications [3]. Foot ulcers are a common

More Information

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complication of diabetes that is not being managed through methods such as diet, exercise, and insulin treatment. Ulcers are formed as a result of skin tissue breaking down and exposing the layers underneath. They're most common under big toes and the balls of feet, and they can affect feet down to the bones. All people with diabetes can develop foot ulcers, but good foot care can help prevent them [4]. Poor blood circulation is a form of vascular disease in which blood doesn't flow to the feet efficiently. Poor circulation can also make it more difficult for ulcers to heal. High can slow the healing process of an infected foot ulcer, so blood sugar management is critical. People with type 2 diabetes and other ailments often have a harder time fighting off infections from ulcers. Nerve damage is a long-term effect and can lead to a loss of feeling in your feet [5]. Intensive glycaemic control delays the onset and slows the progression of diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy in patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. However, intensive glycaemic control must also be accompanied by cautious monitoring as tighter control of glycaemic state could lead to profound hypoglycaemia. [6]. The development of a diabetic foot ulcer begins with a callus from neuropathy. The loss of sensation results in ongoing trauma, skin breakdown, and ulcer development. Patients with diabetes mellitus often experience poor circulation from atherosclerosis and vascular damage, which inhibits wound healing and can lead to tissue necrosis and gangrene. 60% of patients with diabetes will develop neuropathy, increasing the risk of foot ulcers. Ulcers most commonly occur on the plantar surface of the foot, including the heel and tips of hammer toes [7].

Materials and Methods

Ethical Consideration

Permission was taken from hospital manager, assist and General Director of Nursing Affairs in King Fahad general hospital Jeddah June 2018.

Study Design

This is an interventional quasi-experimental hospital-based study was conduct in King Fahd General Hospital in Jeddah, king of Saudi Arabia.

Study Area

The study will be carry out at selected in patients and out patients who are following up in diabetic foot clinic at King Fahad General Hospital in Jeddah, king of Saudi Arabia. King Fahad hospital Jeddah is one of biggest hospital under ministry of health in region in kingdom of Saudi Arabia with 1000 bed capacity. Wound Management and Diabetic Foot Unit is one of department that is providing in-patient and out-patient service who is suffering from chronic wound in general and in Diabetic foot specially.

Study Population

The in patients and out patients who are following up in diabetic foot clinic at King Fahad General Hospital in Jeddah, king of Saudi. During the period (August 2018 to August 2021).

Sample size

Sixty diabetics' available patients in the selected areas in patients and out patients, who are following up in diabetic foot clinic at King Fahad General Hospital in Jeddah, king of Saudi. During the period of the study were includes in the study from (August 2018 to august 2021)

Study duration

The duration of study was from (August 2018 to August 2021).

Inclusion criteria

All available sixty patients in patients who are following up in diabetic foot clinic at King Fahad General Hospital in Jeddah King of Saudi, during the period of study

Exclusion criteria

All patients who are not available at the time of study.

Data collection tools

Data will be collected by the investigator using structured closed ended questionnaire to assess health education program in knowledge, practices, and attitudes of diabetic Septic Foot patients.

Phase of study

Phase One

A structure pre questionnaire will be design by the researcher including data about socio-demographic characteristics, data about the patients knowledge, practice and attitudes regarding lifestyle during Diabetic Septic Foot in the setting Hospital during the period of the study from (Augus2018 to August 2021)

Phase Two

Design educational program for patients about caring regarding Prevention and Control of Diabetic Septic Foot at King Fahad General Hospital in Jeddah, king of Saudi Arabia.

Phase three

Post questionnaire will be design by the researcher including data about the patients' knowledge practice and attitudes regarding lifestyle during diabetic foot in the setting Hospital.

Selection and Description of Participants

Clearly describe the selection of observational or experimental participants (healthy individuals or patients, including controls), including eligibility and exclusion criteria and a description of the source population. Because the relevance of such variables as age, sex, or ethnicity is not always known at the time of study design, researchers should aim for inclusion of representative populations into all study types and at a minimum provide descriptive data for these and other relevant demographic variables. Comment on

Statistics

The data were coded, entered, and analyzed using the statistical package for social Science (SPSS) version (23), the data were presented in form of percentage.

Table 1: Results of Diabetic Patients According to Their Knowledge Regarding Causes of Diabetic Foot Ulcers

Causes of diabetic ulcers foot	Pre-intervention				Post-intervention				Total	
	Correct		Incorrect		Correct		Incorrect		No	%
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%		
Poor circulation	36	59	25	41	55	90.2	6	9.8	61	100
High blood sugar	32	52.5	29	47.5	49	80.3	12	19.7	61	100
Nerve damage	27	44.3	34	55.7	42	68.9	19	31.1	61	100
Irritated or wounded feet	40	65.6	21	34.4	54	88.5	7	11.5	61	100

Table 2: Results of Diabetic Patients' Knowledge According to Their Knowledge Regarding Surgical Management

Surgical management	Pre				Post				Total	
	Correct		Incorrect		Correct		Incorrect		No	%
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%		
Surgical management to improve soft tissue cover is recommended.	35	57.4	26	42.6	48	78.7	13	21.3	61	100
Chronic foot ulcer not amenable to treatment with therapeutic footwear or off-loading techniques	23	37.7	38	62.3	41	67.2	20	32.8	61	100
All infected tissues are to be removed	34	55.7	27	44.3	49	80.3	12	19.7	61	100
Amputation done for gangrenous parts.	28	45.9	33	54.1	42	68.9	19	31.1	61	100
It is performed to allow optimum function of the remaining foot.	31	50.8	30	49.2	53	86.9	8	13.1	61	100

Table 3: Results of Diabetic Patients' Knowledge According to Their Knowledge Regarding Risk Factors for Diabetic Foot Ulcers

Risk factors for diabetic foot ulcers	Pre- intervention				Post- intervention				Total	
	Correct		Incorrect		Correct		Incorrect		No	%
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%		
Poor quality shoes	38	62.3	23	37.7	50	82	11	18	61	100
Poor hygiene	51	83.6	10	16.4	54	88.5	7	11.5	61	100
Improper trimming of toenails	38	62.3	23	37.7	49	80.3	12	19.7	61	100
Eye disease from diabetes	34	55.7	27	44.3	54	88.5	7	11.5	61	100
Heart disease	35	57.4	26	42.6	51	83.6	10	16.4	61	100
Kidney disease	42	68.9	19	31.1	51	83.6	10	16.4	61	100
Obesity	46	75.4	15	24.6	59	96.7	2	3.3	61	100
Tobacco use	42	68.9	19	31.1	58	95.1	3	4.9	61	100
Neuropathy	24	39.3	37	60.7	42	68.9	19	31.1	61	100
Abnormal foot pressures	38	62.3	23	37.7	58	95.1	3	4.9	61	100
Hyperglycemia	32	52.5	29	47.5	52	85.2	9	14.8	61	100
Trauma	44	72.1	17	27.9	57	93.4	4	6.6	61	100

Results and Discussion

The results of diabetic patients according to cause of diabetics foot ulcers presented high increased percentage for correct questions in post-intervention which ranged between (68.6 to 90.2%) compared to (44.3 to 65.6%) for correct in pre-intervention .The results of incorrect questions in post-intervention presented highly decreased percentage ranged between (31.1 to 9.8%) for incorrect questions compared to incorrect questions which ranged between (55.7 to 34.4%) in pre-intervention Table 1, these results are similar to results of Adeyemim *et al.*,

2021 [1]., they stated patients knowledge regarded cause of diabetic foot ulcers, were raised in post-intervention compared to pre-intervention also (Coffey, L., *et al.*, (2019) [8], they stated that the patients' knowledge was improved after education session regarded prevention and management of foot ulcer the mean of patients' knowledge regarding preventive measures and management of diabetic complications. The results of diabetic patients knowledge regarding the risk factors for diabetic foot ulcers presented increased in percentage ranged between (96.7 to 85.2%) in pre-

intervention for correct questions compared to 52.5 to 83.6) in pre-intervention. The results of incorrect question in post-intervention presented decreased percentage ranged between (3.3 to 19.7%) compared to (60.7 to 16.4 In pre-intervention Table 3. These results in agreement with Brabd *et al.*, [9], whom reported that there was significant improvement in reported foot care behavior after education session which was similar to this study. In study done by Magbanual *et al* [10], patients who received diabetes education training were twice as likely to have a good knowledge score, which support the finding of present study. A proper foot care instruction program has been shown to lower of ulceration [11,12].

The results of diabetic patients' knowledge according to their knowledge regarding surgical management presented increase for correct questions in post-intervention ranged between (6.7 to 86.9%), compared to pre-intervention correct which ranged (37.7 to 57.4). the results of incorrect question presented light decreased in post-intervention percentage ranged between (13.1 to 32.8%) compared to (62.3 to 42.6%) for incorrect questions in pre-intervention Table 3. Finding from this study support the appropriate diabetes education and preventive care can reduce the fear of foot ulcers and amputations. Revera (2009) [13], reported that meticulous foot care and proper patients' education has been reported to reduce the amputation rate associated with diabetes by 50 %.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there was significant improvement in patients' knowledge attitude and practice regarding diabetic septic foot care after the training program.

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Conflict of Interests

There is no conflict of interest.

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